

Octave - A (very) brief introduction

J. Belinha*

School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto, Department Mechanical Engineering, Rua Dr. Antonio Bernardino de Almeida, 431, Porto, Portugal - email: job@isep.ipp.pt

SUMMARY

This manuscript aims to deliver a brief introduction to Octave programming for engineering and mathematics applications. It was written for under-graduated students, to help them with their own class projects and assignments. Thus, section 1 introduces the basics of Octave, conventions and operations and it also provided the web link for downloading Octave. Since Octave is particularly suited to perform operations dealing vectors and matrices, section 2 introduces how Octave handles such structures. Besides basic operations, indexing and solving operations are also demonstrated. Then, in section 3, Octave user functions are presented. Programming structures, such as loops, branching and Boolean operations are presented with detail, and how Octave deals with time and saves/loads information is also shown. Octave is particularly useful to plot user friendly graphics. Thus, section 4 is dedicated to the presentation of popular 2D and 3D graphical solutions offered by Octave, such as: plot, scatter, trimesh and tetramesh graphical functions. In the end, in section 5, chief conclusions and final remarks are addressed.
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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

GNU-Octave, or simply Octave, is a high-level programming language, developed for numerical computations. It is particularly suited for vectorizable numerical calculations and being used for solving linear and nonlinear equations, numerical linear algebra, statistical analysis. Octave is a freely redistributable open-source software. The users can redistribute it and/or modify it under the terms of the GNU General Public License as published by the Free Software Foundation. Any one can freely download Octave from GNU-Octave site: <https://www.gnu.org/software/octave/>

Since the syntax of Octave resembles Matlab®, an Octave script usually runs on Matlab® without requiring any modification. However, the opposite is not always true. Being a commercial software, Matlab® possesses much more available functions and add-on toolboxes, unavailable in Octave (at least, not available yet).

After downloading Octave, install it and you are ready to start programming. This support text was prepared using GNU Octave 6.4.0. (2022) version.

*Correspondence to: J.Belinha, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto, Department Mechanical Engineering, Rua Dr. Antonio Bernardino de Almeida, 431, Porto, Portugal - job@isep.ipp.pt

1.2. Help

Help will always be given at Octave to those who deserve it. Ring a bell? Today, with the widespread of internet users and topics, it is relatively easy to find the right answer to a specific question using a web search-engine. Nevertheless, caution is required. Anyone can post a solution in the vast web, it does not mean it is the right solution. One always must maintain a critical spirit. We can trust on GNU-Octave official web page (<https://www.gnu.org/software/octave/>), which provided a detailed manual on all the developed Octave's functions, and on specialized Octave forums.

Despite all the help on the internet, Octave's also possesses an internal function that describes how an Octave's internal function works - the **help** function.

If, in Octave's command window, is written:

```
octave>> help det
```

In Octave's command window, will appear a detailed description of **det** built-in function, how it works and how it can be used. Try it, is free.

1.3. Input conventions

As any other programming language, Octave's possesses some input conventions. Being this text a brief introduction, only the basics are mentioned.

All the commands can be written directly on the command window. This allows to test simple algorithms or calculate simple algebraic operations. However, a pipe.line of commands can also be organized on a script, saved and then the script is called from the command windows. The final result will be the same.

Octave is capable to run previously written scripts, which are plain text files with file suffix ".m". For instance, observe the following script:

```
1 % this is an example of a simple script: example_script.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 a=1;
6 b=2
7 c(1,1)=a;
8 c(2,1)=b,
9 d=[a,b]; % comments can be inserted after the command
10 e=c*d;
11 f=[4,5;3,-1];
12 g=0.5*e+2.1*f ... % line break
13 +4.5*e*f;
14 h=4*g+f, k=h-e;
15 m=h*k; n=2*h*e;
16 G=0.9*e*f;
```

Listing 1: Example of a simple script: example_script.m

After writing, in Octave's command window,

```
octave>> example_script
```

The lines of **example_script.m** are imported to Octave's command window (notice that the file was called without the suffix ".m") and its content is executed line by line.

If a command ends with ";", it means that its result will not be displayed on the command window. On the other hand, if "," is used to terminate the command (as in line 8) or the command is terminated without ";" (as in line 6), its results will be printed as on-screen output.

It is possible to write several commands on the same line, however, they have to be separated by ";" or ",". Once again, if they are separated by ";", the corresponding result

<	smaller
<=	smaller or equal
>	greater
>=	greater or equal
==	equal
~=	not equal
&&	and
	or
~	not

Table I. Logical Operators in Octave.

will not be displayed (as in line 15). If they are separated by ";", the corresponding previous command will be printed on screen. For instance, line 14, variable h will be printed on-screen and variable k will not.

Comments are very useful. They are personal notes of the programmer to others (or, most of the times, to himself). They allow to understand more easily the code. Octave does not read comments. A comment is a text preceded by `%`. It can occupy an entire line (see line 1), or it can start after a command (see lines 9 and 12).

Sometimes a command is too long, it involves many operations. Then, in order to ease its reading, it is necessary to break it. Octave allows to break a command (or expression) using `"..."`, which denotes that the expression continues into the next line, as shown in lines 12 and 13. After the break command `"..."`, it is always possible to include a comment (see line 12).

Finally, Octave is case sensitive. The result from line 12 will not conflict with the result of line 16. Octave distinguishes between g and G .

1.4. Variables and standard operations

As in any other programming language, variables are obtained by declaring an equality operation, such as the one presented in lines 1 to 16 of the script on Listing 1. For instances, a is a variable defined as $a = 1$ and c is a variable vector defined as $c = \{1, 2\}^T$.

Octave is a programming language to build engineering and mathematical applications. Thus, all standard mathematical operations and functions are available, such as: `+`, `-`, `*`, `/`, `sin`, `cos`, `exp`, `acos`, `abs`, etc.

Additionally, as table I operators for elementary logic are also available:

Octave possesses a graphical user interface (GUI), which simplifies the debugging. Nevertheless, when debugging user-defined entities, the following commands can be used:

- **whos**: it shows all user-defined variables and functions.
- **type phy**: it displays information about the variable or function named "phy" on the screen.

Additionally, it is useful to clear the memory and the work-space before starting a new program execution.

- **clc**: clears the screen of the command window.
- **clear all**: erases all variables from the memory.
- **clear phy fi**: erases from the memory only the declared variables, in this case: **phy** and **fi**.
- **close all**: Closes all figures produced by previous scripts.

2. VECTORS & MATRICES

2.1. Vectors

Octave allows to define vectors using explicit commands, or using automatic generation. For instance, consider the following vectors:

$$\vec{a} = \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \vec{b} = \begin{Bmatrix} 3 \\ 5 \\ 7 \\ 9 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \vec{c} = \vec{a}^T = \{ 1 \ 2 \ 3 \} \quad (1)$$

These vectors can be defined using the commands on the script presented in Listing 2.

```

1 % script: vectors1.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 % ***** vector a:
6 a(1,1)=1; % individual component
7 a(2,1)=2;
8 a(3,1)=3;
9 a=[1;2;3]; % column vector
10 % ***** vector b:
11 b(1,1)=3; % individual component
12 b(2,1)=5;
13 b(3,1)=7;
14 b(4,1)=9;
15 b=[3;5;7;9]; % column vector
16 b=3:2:9; % automatic generation with constant increment
17 % ***** vector c:
18 c(1,1)=1; % individual component
19 c(1,2)=2;
20 c(1,3)=3;
21 c=[1,2,3]; % row vector
22 c=[1;2;3]'; % transpose

```

Listing 2: Example of a script containing vector definition: **vectors1.m**

A vector can be defined declaring each component, as lines 6 to 8 show for vector \vec{a} and lines 11 to 14 and lines 18 to 20 show for vectors \vec{b} and \vec{c} , respectively. Alternatively, all components of a vector can be defined in one command line, as represented in lines 9, 15 and 21, correspondingly for vectors \vec{a} , \vec{b} and \vec{c} .

One of the most useful functionalities of Octave is the possibility to define the vector using the automatic generation with constant increment, as line 16 shows. From equation 1 it is perceptible that the first component of vector \vec{b} is 3 and the following components are increments of 2 until the number 9 is reached. Thus, it is possible to build it with the automatic generator. There are several cases in which very large vectors can be defined using the automatic generator, such as space or time discretization vectors

2.2. Matrices

With Octave it is possible to define and perform several useful operations with matrices, easing its manipulation. Consider the following matrices,

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 5 \\ 4 & 7 & 8 \end{bmatrix} ; \quad [B] = \begin{bmatrix} 9 & 6 \\ 5 & 7 \\ 0 & 4 \end{bmatrix} ; \quad [C] = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 2 & 1 & 9 & 6 \\ 1 & 3 & 5 & 5 & 7 \\ 4 & 7 & 8 & 0 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

They can be constructed using the commands of the script in Listing 3.

```

1 % script: matrices1.m
2 clc
3 clear all

```

```

4 close all
5 % ***** matrix A:
6 A(1,1)=3; A(1,2)=2; A(1,3)=1; % individual component
7 A(2,1)=1; A(2,2)=3; A(2,3)=5;
8 A(3,1)=4; A(3,2)=7; A(3,3)=8;
9 A=[3,2,1;1,3,5;4,7,8]; % one step definition
10 % ***** matrix B:
11 B(1,1)=9; B(1,2)=6; % individual component
12 B(2,1)=5; B(2,2)=7;
13 B(3,1)=0; B(3,2)=4;
14 B=[9,6;5,7;0,4]; % one step definition
15 % ***** matrix C:
16 C = [A B]; % submatrices assemblage
17 % ***** matrix functions
18 n=5;m=4;
19 D=eye(n,m);
20 E=zeros(n,m);
21 F=ones(n,m);
22 G=rand(n,m);

```

Listing 3: Example of a script containing matrices definition: **matrices1.m**

For small matrices, declaring individually each component of the matrix is still possible (see lines 6 to 8 for matrix $[A]$ and lines 11 to 13 for matrix $[B]$). However, for larger matrices such procedure is highly inefficient. Another way to declare a matrix is declaring the matrix in one single step, as lines 9 and 14 show for matrices $[A]$ and $[B]$, respectively.

Another interesting functionality of octave is the assemblage of matrices, allowing to construct larger matrices. For instance, from equation 2, it is perceptible that matrix $[C]$ is a combination of matrix $[A]$ and $[B]$: $[C] = [[A][B]]$. Thus, Octave allows to define matrix $[C]$ automatically using the assemblage of sub-matrices, as line 16 shows.

Octave offers some tools to initialize matrices. If the memory space of a matrix is already pre-allocated, its manipulation and component definition will be much faster, reducing its computational cost. Thus, Octave possesses the following built-in functions:

- **eye(n,m)**: generates a matrix with dimension $n \times m$, with ones (1) along the main diagonal and zeros in all other components. If $n = m$, then the identity matrix is generated.
- **zeros(n,m)**: generates a zero matrix with dimensions $n \times m$.
- **ones(n,m)**: generates a matrix with dimensions $n \times m$, in which all components are ones (1).
- **rand(n,m)**: generates a matrix with dimensions $n \times m$, in which all components are random values uniformly distributed in the interval $[0, 1]$.

The script in Listing 3 provides some examples from lines 18 to 22.

2.3. Basic Operations

Octave allows fast algebraic calculations with matrices and vectors. In Listing 4 it is possible to find some standard matrix operations.

```

1 % script: matrices2.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 % ***** matrix A:
6 A=[3,2,1;1,3,5;4,7,8]; % one step definition
7 % ***** matrix B:
8 B=[9,6;5,7;0,4]; % one step definition
9 % ***** scalar multiplication:
10 C=3.1*A;
11 % ***** sum
12 D=A+C;
13 % ***** subtraction
14 E=D-C;

```

```

15 % ***** matrix multiplication
16 F=A*B;
17 G=E*D;
18 % ***** transposing
19 H=A';
20 J=B';
21 % ***** element-wise multiplication
22 K=D.*E; % Hadamard product
23 L=D.*2;
24 % ***** element-wise power
25 M=A.^D;
26 N=A.^2;

```

Listing 4: Example of a script containing matrix basic operations: **matrices2.m**

After defining the matrices $[A]$ and $[B]$ in lines 6 and 8, it is possible:

- to obtain matrix $[C]$ by multiplying all the components of matrix $[A]$ by 3.1 (see line 10), $c_{ij} = 3.1 \cdot a_{ij}$.
- to obtain matrix $[D]$ by adding matrix $[A]$ with matrix $[C]$, $d_{ij} = a_{ij} + c_{ij}$, as line 12 shows (both matrices $[A]$ and $[C]$ have to possess the same dimension).
- to obtain matrix $[E]$ by subtracting matrix $[C]$ to matrix $[D]$, $e_{ij} = d_{ij} - c_{ij}$, as line 14 shows (both matrices $[C]$ and $[D]$ have to possess the same dimension).
- to obtain matrix $[F]$ by multiplying matrices $[A]$ and $[B]$, as line 16 shows.
- to obtain the transpose of matrix $[A]$, $h_{ij} = a_{ji}$, or matrix $[B]$, as lines 19 and 20 shows.
- to calculate the Hadamard product, $k_{ij} = d_{ij} \cdot e_{ij}$, using the element-wise multiplication (line 22), or to multiply each component of matrix $[D]$ by 2 (line 23), which produces the same result as already presented in line 10.
- to obtain a new matrix $[M]$ by powering each component a_{ij} of matrix $[A]$ with the corresponding component d_{ij} of matrix $[D]$, $m_{ij} = (a_{ij})^{d_{ij}}$, as line 25 shows.

2.4. Indexing

Octave allows to work directly with the indexes of the matrices, reducing the computational cost associated with its manipulation. In Listing 5 it is presented a script with some relevant indexing manipulations.

```

1 % script: matrices3.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 % ***** matrix A:
6 A=[3,2,1,0;1,3,5,8;4,7,8,9;3,4,5,7];
7 % ***** vector B:
8 b=[9;5;4;2];
9 % ***** defining variables by index:
10 c=b(3);
11 d=b(3,1);
12 e=A(2,3);
13 f=A(3,1:3);
14 g=b(2:3,1);
15 h=A(2,:);
16 j=A(:,3);
17 % ***** dimensions
18 k=length(b); % number of components
19 [rows,columns]=size(A); % number of rows/columns
20 % ***** reshaping
21 B=diag(A);
22 C=diag(b);
23 A(3,:)=b'; % substitutes the 3rd row
24 A(:,2)=b; % substitutes the 2nd column
25 A(:,1)=[]; % deletes the 4th column
26 A(4,:)=[]; % deletes the 4th row

```

Listing 5: Example of a script containing indexing manipulations: **matrices3.m**

After defining matrix $[A]$ and vector \vec{b} , lines 6 and 8, it is possible to perform some indexing operations.

- **c=b(3)**: retrieves the third element of vector \vec{b} , which is the same as: **c=b(3,1)**, lines 10 and 11.
- **e=A(2,3)**: retrieves the component on the second row and third column of matrix $[A]$, line 12.
- **f=A(3,1:3)**: retrieves the following row vector: $\vec{f} = \{a_{3,1}, a_{3,2}, a_{3,3}\}$, line 13.
- **g=A(2:3,1)**: retrieves the following column vector: $\vec{g} = \{a_{2,1}, a_{3,1}\}^T$, line 14.
- **h=A(2,:)**: retrieves the following row vector: $\vec{h} = \{a_{2,1}, a_{2,2}, a_{2,3}, a_{2,4}\}$, line 15.
- **h=A(2,:)**: retrieves the following column vector: $\vec{j} = \{a_{1,3}, a_{2,3}, a_{3,3}, a_{4,3}\}^T$, line 16.

It is also very important to know the dimensions of vectors and matrices. Octave offers such tools. The command **length** provides the number of rows or columns of a row-vector or a column vectors, respectively (see line 18). The command **size** is even more general. It provides the number of rows and columns of an array (matrix or vector), as line 19 shows. Additionally, Octave permits other useful matrix manipulations. Thus,

- **B=diag(A)**: creates a new matrix $[B]$ with the only non-zero diagonal components. The diagonal components of matrix $[B]$ are equal to the diagonal components of matrix $[A]$, line 21.
- **C=diag(b)**: creates a new matrix $[C]$ with the only non-zero diagonal components. The diagonal components of matrix $[C]$ are equal to the components of vector \vec{b} , line 22.
- **A(3,:)=b'**: the third row of matrix $[A]$ is completely substituted by the transpose of vector \vec{b} , line 23.
- **A(:,2)=b**: the second column of matrix $[A]$ is completely substituted by vector \vec{b} , line 24.
- **A(:,1)=[]**: the first column of matrix $[A]$ is deleted, line 25.
- **A(4,1)=[]**: the fourth row of matrix $[A]$ is deleted, line 26.

2.5. Solving operations

Octave possesses powerful numerical tools to solve, invert, decompose and find the eigenvalues of matrices. Some corresponding relevant Octave's built-in function are presented in Listing 6.

```

1 % script: matrices4.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 % ***** matrix A:
6 A=[3, 2, 1, 0; 1, 3, 5, 8; 4, 7, 8, 9; 3, 4, 5, 7];
7 % ***** vector B:
8 b=[9; 5; 4; 2];
9 % ***** solving Ax=b
10 x=A\b; % solves the equation: Ax=b
11 % ***** inverse
12 B=inv(A); % computes the inverse of A
13 % ***** decomposition
14 [L,U,P]=lu(A); % computes the LU-decomposition: LU=PA
15 [Q,R]=qr(A); % computes the QR-decomposition: QR=A$
16 % ***** eigen-values and vectors
17 [V,D]=eig(A); % computes a eigenvalues and eigenvectors of A
18 % ***** norms and condition numbers
19 N=norm(b,2); % calculates the 2-norm of vector b
20 c=cond(A); % computes the condition number of A

```

Listing 6: Example of a script containing Octave's numerical tools for matrices: **matrices4.m**

Thus,

- $\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{A}\backslash\mathbf{b}$: solves the system of equations $A \cdot x = b$, line 10.
- $\mathbf{B}=\mathbf{inv}(\mathbf{A})$: calculates the inverse matrix of $[A]$, line 12. It can be also used to solve the system of equations $[A] \cdot \vec{x} = \vec{b}$ with: $\vec{x} = [A]^{-1} \cdot \vec{b}$. However, it will be much slower than the procedure of line 10.
- $[\mathbf{L},\mathbf{U},\mathbf{P}]=\mathbf{lu}(\mathbf{A})$: calculates the LU-decomposition $LU = PA$, line 14.
- $[\mathbf{Q},\mathbf{R}]=\mathbf{qr}(\mathbf{A})$: calculates the QR-decomposition $QR = A$, line 15.
- $[\mathbf{Q},\mathbf{R}]=\mathbf{qr}(\mathbf{A})$: calculates a diagonal matrix D , with the eigen-values of A , and a matrix V with the corresponding eigen-vectors. In the end, the following relation is verified: $AV = VD$, line 17.
- $\mathbf{N}=\mathbf{norm}(\mathbf{b},2)$: computes the 2-norm of vector b . If b is a matrix, 2 can only take the values 1, 2 or *inf*. If omitted, the default is $p = 2$, line 19.
- $\mathbf{c}=\mathbf{cond}(\mathbf{A})$: calculates the condition number of matrix A with respect to the 2-norm, line 20.

3. CONTROL STRUCTURES

3.1. Functions

In Octave, functions are saved as a script - with the suffix ".m". However, in opposition to scripts, all variables used inside the function are local, i.e., the variables within the function do not influence the variables outside the functions (used after or previously). In order to better understand a function, consider the following script presented in Listing 7.

```

1 % script: scri_4_func.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 % ***** variables
6 t=0:1:100; % vector time (in seconds)
7 a=2.1; % alpha parameter
8 g=0.5; % gamma parameter
9 % ***** calling function func1
10 [v1,c1] = func1(t,a,g);
11 % ***** calling function func2
12 [k1,k2,v2] = func2(v1,c1);
13 % ***** calling function func3
14 [info] = func3(v1,c1);

```

Listing 7: Example of a script containing functions: **scri4func.m**

Within the script, three functions are called: **func1.m**, **func2.m** and **func3.m**, in lines 10, 12 and 14, respectively. Functions are called with arguments. For example, function **func1.m** requires the input of variables \vec{t} , a and g , and outputs variables \vec{v}_1 and c_1 , as in equation 3,

$$\vec{v}_1 = \sin(a) \cdot \vec{t} \quad ; \quad h_1 = a \cdot g^2; \quad ; \quad c_1 = h_1 + \cos(g); \quad (3)$$

Opening function **func1.m**, Listing 8, it is possible to visualize that a function starts with the declaration **function**, followed by the output arguments, the function name and the input arguments. It is a good practice to explain the input/output arguments used, in order to clarify other users (lines 3 to 9). Next, in lines 10 to 12, the output variables are obtained, \vec{v}_1 and c_1 .

```

1 % function func1.m
2 function [v1,c1] = func1(t,a,g);
3 % input:
4 % t: vector [1xn]
5 % a: scalar
6 % g: scalar

```

```

7 % output:
8 % v1: vector [1xn]
9 % c1: scalar
10 v1 = sin(a)*t;
11 h1 = a*g^2;
12 c1 = h1*cos(g);

```

Listing 8: Example of functions containing simple operations. **func1.m**

Notice that an auxiliary variable was used inside **func1.m**: $h1$. However, since that variable is only being used inside the function, in the global work space there is no record of $h1$. If $h1$ is an important variable, that should be preserved, in script **scri4func.m**, after line 4, it should be declared: **global h1**, and also in **func1.m**, after line 2, the same should be included: **global h1**. With this, if $h1$ is modified inside or outside any function/script, its value is automatically updated. This feature should be used with caution, because what happens inside a function should stay inside the function.

3.2. Loops

Loops are very useful built in functions that allow to perform recurrent operations. With loops it is possible to construct new vector and matrices, and also recurrently update variables. However, it is always much more efficient to vectorized operations than use loop operations. In Listing 7, function **func2.m** includes three kinds of loops. As Listing 9 shows, function **func2.m** first obtains the size of row-vector $\vec{v}_1: n_v$.

```

1 % function func2.m
2 function [k1,k2,v2] = func2(v1,c1);
3 % input:
4 % v1: vector [1xn]
5 % c1: scalar
6 % output:
7 % k1: scalar
8 % k2: scalar
9 % v2: vector [1xn]
10 nv = length(v1); % size of vector v1
11 % ***** loop over nv
12 k1 = 0;
13 for ii = 1:nv
14     k1 = k1+c1*cos(pi*v1(1,ii))^v1(1,ii);
15 end
16 % ***** while
17 q1 = 0.1;
18 k2 = 0;
19 ind = 0;
20 while k2 < c1
21     ind = ind + 1;
22     k2 = k2 + q1^ind;
23 end
24 % ***** loop backward
25 v2 = zeros(1,nv);
26 for ii = nv:-1:1
27     jj = nv-(ii-1);
28     v2(1,ii)=c1*v1(1,jj);
29 end

```

Listing 9: Example of loops containing simple operations. **func2.m**

Then, from line 12 to 15, a first loop is presented using function **for**. This is the default loop in Octave. Variable ii will increment from 1 to n_v with unitary values. First, $ii = 1$, then $ii = 2$, after $ii = 3$, until $ii = n_v$. Inside the loop, scalar variable k_1 will modify (increment) its value as ii grows from 1 to n_v , as the expression:

$$k_1 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_v} c_1 \cdot \cos(\pi \cdot (v_1)_i^{(v_1)_i}) \quad (4)$$

In lines 17 to 23, another type of loop is presented: **while**. This function performs the loop until the condition in front of the **while** is satisfied (**k2<c1**). When using a **while** loop,

caution is necessary because a **while** loop can never end if the condition is not satisfied. Generally, an additional condition is inserted to ensure that the loop ends, such as: **while** $k_2 < c_1 \ || \ \text{ind} > 1000$. This way, the **while** loop is terminated after 1000 iterations:

$$k_2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_v} 0.1^i, \quad n_v = 1000 \quad \vee \quad k_2 < c_1 \quad (5)$$

The loop function **for** is very flexible. For instances, it is possible to start from n_v and then, decrease (iterative steps of -1) until 1, as lines 25 to 29 shows. This is useful operation is called the backward loop. More, the increment amount can be defined as pleased. For instance, it can be defined an increment set of 4: **for** $ii = 1:4:500$, which will produce: $ii = 1$, then $ii = 5$, after $ii = 9$, until a ii passes reaches 500 (if $ii > 500$, the loop stops).

A loop always ends with a **end**.

3.3. Branching and Boolean operations

Octave also allows to establish branching and Boolean operations. Function **func3.m** In Listing 7, function **func3.m** (presented in Listing 10) shows such operations.

```

1 % function func3.m
2 function [info] = func3(v1,c1);
3 % input:
4 % v1: vector [1xn]
5 % c1: scalar
6 % output:
7 % info: integer vector [nx1]
8 nv = length(v1); % size of vector v1
9 info = zeros(8,1);
10 % ***** loop over nv
11 for ii = 1:nv
12     if v1(1,ii) == 10 % equal
13         info(1,1) = info(1,1) + 1;
14     end
15     if v1(1,ii) ~= 30 % different
16         info(2,1) = info(2,1) + 1;
17     end
18     if v1(1,ii) >= 75 % greater or equal
19         info(3,1) = info(3,1) + 1;
20     elseif v1(1,ii) <= 15 % smaller or equal
21         info(4,1) = info(4,1) + 1;
22     else
23         info(5,1) = info(5,1) + 1;
24     end
25     if v1(1,ii) > 10 && v1(1,ii) < 20 % and
26         info(6,1) = info(6,1) + 1;
27     end
28     if v1(1,ii) < 5 || v1(1,ii) > 95 % or
29         info(7,1) = info(7,1) + 1;
30     end
31 end

```

Listing 10: Example a function containing branching and Boolean operations. **func3.m**

Fist, output column array **info** is initialized. Then, an iterative loop (increment steps of 1) is performed with the size n_v of vector \vec{v}_1 . In lines 12 to 14, it is saved in cell 1 of array **info** the number components of vector \vec{v}_1 that are equal to 10 (condition in line 12). In opposition, in lines 15 to 17, the number of vectorial components different of 30 is saved in cell 2 of array **info** (condition in line 12). In lines 18 to 24, three conditions are contemplated. The number of components of \vec{v}_1 higher than 75 are saved in cell 3 of array **info**, the number of components of \vec{v}_1 lower than 15 are saved in cell 4 of array **info**, and all the other cases number is saved in cell 5 of array **info**.

In lines 25 to 27 is presented an **AND** Boolean condition. Thus, in cell 6 of array **info** is saved the number of \vec{v}_1 components between 10 and 20 (excluding 10 and 20).

An *OR* Boolean condition is shown in lines 28 to 30, in which the number of \vec{v}_1 components higher than 95 and lower than 5 (excluding 5 and 95) is saved in cell 7 of array **info**.

3.4. Saving and loading data

Octave allows to save and load data, as well as print data to the screen. In Listing 11 a simple script is presented.

```

1 % script: ex_save_load.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 k1 = 0;
6 nv = 10;
7 v1 = zeros(1, nv);
8 v2 = v1';
9 for ii = 1:nv
10     k1 = k1+50*cos(pi*1.2^ii);
11     v1(1, ii) = 2.5*sin(pi*1.2^ii);
12     v2(ii, 1) = v1(1, ii)^2;
13 end
14 % ***** saving or loading
15 save filedata1.m
16 save filedata2.m k1 v1
17 load filedata1.m
18 load filedata1.m nv v2
19 % ***** printing on screen
20 fprintf('The values of v1 are: \n');
21 for ii = 1:nv
22     fprintf('%e \n', v1(1, ii));
23 end

```

Listing 11: Example a function containing saving and loading functions. **ex_save_load.m**

After performing several computations, the data can be saved to a file using the function **save**. As line 15 shows, all the data produced in the script (k_1 , n_v , \vec{v}_1 , \vec{v}_2 and ii) is saved in **datafile1.m** because it was not declared any specific data to be saved. In these cases, by default Octave saves all the data into the file. Alternatively, in line 16, with **save datafile2.m k1 v1**, only variables k_1 and \vec{v}_1 are saved into file **datafile2.m**. By saving only relevant variables, the size of the data files is reduced and future loadings are faster. Regarding the loading function, Octave allows to load a previously saved file with the function **load**. As line 17 shows, **load datafile1.m** will load all the variable inside file **datafile1.m**. However, if the variable intended are declared, only those variables will be loaded. Thus, as line 18 shows with **load datafile1.m nv v2**, only n_v and \vec{v}_2 are loaded from **datafile1.m**.

Sometimes, it is useful to print in the screen some results, in order to verify, in certain check points, if the script is performing as expected. Therefore, Octave possesses the functions **fprintf**, which outputs to the screen simple message strings (text), as line 20 shows, or scalar number, as line 22 shows.

3.5. Time

Octave possesses some built-in functions that enable to count the time or to pause the process. The function **pause** pauses the process until a key is pressed. On the other hand, if function **pause** is combined with a number: **pause(27)**, for example, it will suspend the process during 27 seconds.

The function **tic** initiates a time counter, which is interrupted with the function **toc**. Combining them, allow to know (in seconds) the computational time required to perform the operations between the declaration of function **tic** and the declaration of function **toc**.

It is always preferable to vectorize the code, instead using loops. Consider the script in Listing 12. Two vectors, \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 , with the same size, are constructed.

```

1 % script: loop_vector.m
2 clc
3 clear all
4 close all
5 v1 = 1:1:100000;
6 v2 = 3*v1;
7 nv = length(v1);
8 % ***** Loop operation
9 a = 0; % internal product of v1 with v2
10 tic;
11 for ii = 1:nv
12     a = a + v1(1,ii)*v2(1,ii);
13 end
14 toc
15 % ***** vector operation
16 tic
17 b = 0; % internal product of v1 with v2
18 b = v1 * v2';
19 toc

```

Listing 12: Example a function comparing computational times. **loop_vector.m**

It is visible that both vectors are very large (100000 components). Calculating the internal product of $\vec{v}_1 \bullet \vec{v}_2$ using a loop (lines 9 to 14) is 5000 times slower than calculating the same internal product using a vector operation (line 18). Thus, as good practice, always try to vectorize the code. It will become much faster.

4. GRAPHICS

One of the most attracting features of Octave is its efficient graphical representation of results. Low level mathematical programming languages, such as FORTRAN or C, require the construction of specific programs to generate GUIs to graphically represent the results. Octave possesses several built-in functions capable to automatically generate 2D or 3D graphics.

4.1. 2D graphics

One of the most useful graphical commands is the **plot** function. Consider vector $\vec{x} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 1000\}$ and the following function,

$$f(x) = 1 + x^2 \cdot \|\sin(x) \cdot \cos(x)\| \quad (6)$$

Such function can be plotted using Octave's **plot** function as shown in Listing 13.

```

1 % script showing some features of the plot function: plot2dfunc.m
2 clc;
3 close all;
4 clear all;
5 x = 1:1:1000;
6 s = length(x);
7 f = zeros(1, s);
8 for ii = 1:s
9     f(1,ii) = 1+x(1,ii)^2*abs(sin(x(1,ii))*cos(x(1,ii)));
10 end
11 figure(1) % figure 1
12 plot(x, f);
13 grid;
14 figure(2) % figure 2
15 semilogx(x, f, 'r. ');
16 grid;
17 figure(3) % figure 3
18 semilogy(x, f, 'g. ');
19 grid;
20 figure(4) % figure 4
21 loglog(x, f, 'k.- ');

```

22 `grid;`

Listing 13: Script with variants of the plot function. **plot2dfunc.m**

The results produced with the code of Listing 13 are shown in figure 1. It is possible to observe in figure 1(a) that if the type and color of the line is not declared (line 12), the default line is solid and blue. The other figures show that it is possible to plot other kinds of lines (dashed, pointed, etc.) and other colours. Further explanations can be found with **help plot**. Other interesting Octave functions are:

- **semilogx**, which plots with the Ox axis in logarithmic scale (line 15 and figure 1(b));
- **semilogy**, which plots with the Oy axis in logarithmic scale (line 18 and figure 1(c));
- **loglog**, which plots both Ox and Oy axis in logarithmic scale (line 21 and figure 1(d));

Notice that the logarithmic scale is of base 10.

In order to show some further Octave's 2D plotting functions, a simple script is written to generate a structured nodal mesh and the corresponding triangular mesh, Listing 14.

```

1 % Structured 2D nodal mesh script: mesh2d.m
2 clc;
3 close all;
4 clear all;
5 L = 20; % dimension along Ox
6 D = 10; % dimension along Oy
7 div_L = 40; % number of division along Ox
8 div_D = 20; % number of division along Oy
9 % ***** nodal mesh
10 ind = 0; % counter
11 x_nod = zeros(3,1); % initialization of vector: x_nod
12 for ii = 1:div_L+1
13     for jj = 1:div_D+1
14         ind = ind + 1;
15         x_nod(1,ind) = (L/div_L)*(ii-1); % x coordinate
16         x_nod(2,ind) = (D/div_D)*(jj-1); % y coordinate
17         x_nod(3,ind) = 0; % z coordinate (2D: z=0)
18     end
19 end
20 num_x = ind; % number of nodes discretizing the problem's domain
21 % ***** triangle mesh (triangular elements)
22 ind = 0;
23 e_nod = zeros(1,3); % initialization of vector: e_nod
24 for ii = 1:div_L
25     for jj = 1:div_D
26         n1 = (jj+0) + (ii-1)*(div_D+1);
27         n2 = (jj+1) + (ii-1)*(div_D+1);
28         n3 = (jj+1) + (ii-0)*(div_D+1);
29         n4 = (jj+0) + (ii-0)*(div_D+1);
30         % first triangle
31         ind = ind + 1;
32         e_nod(ind,1:3) = [n1 n2 n4];
33         % second triangle
34         ind = ind + 1;
35         e_nod(ind,1:3) = [n2 n3 n4];
36     end
37 end
38 num_e = ind; % number of elements discretizing the problem's domain

```

Listing 14: Script for constructing 2D structured meshes. **mesh2d.m**

This script generates a nodal mesh and a triangular mesh organized in arrays **x_nod** and **e_nod**, respectively. Both arrays, correspondingly represented as $[x]$ and $[e]$, are organized as:

$$[x] = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_N \\ y_1 & y_2 & \cdots & y_N \\ z_1 & z_2 & \cdots & z_N \end{bmatrix} ; [e] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 4 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ N & N-2 & N-1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Thus, array **x_nod** contains the coordinates of each node of the nodal mesh and possesses a size $[3 \times N]$, being N the total number of nodes of the nodal mesh. With size $[N_e \times 3]$, being N_e the total number of triangles of the triangular mesh, array **e_nod** possesses in each line the index of the nodes forming the corresponding triangle.

In Listing 15 some very useful 2D plotting features of Octave are presented, particularly for numerical methods discretization techniques.

```

1 % Plotting a structured 2D nodal mesh script: plot2dmesh.m
2 mesh2d; % calling mesh2d script
3 % ***** plotting the nodal mesh
4 figure(1)
5 plot(x_nod(1,:),x_nod(2:,:), 'ko');
6 axis equal;
7 % ***** scatter plot function
8 f=zeros(1,num_x);
9 for ii = 1:num_x
10     f(1,ii) = x_nod(1,ii)*x_nod(2,ii);
11 end
12 figure(2)
13 var_field = f;
14 hold on;
15 colorbar;
16 caxis([min(var_field) max(var_field)]);
17 scatter(x_nod(1,:)', x_nod(2,:)', 20, var_field, 'filled')
18 colorbar; % colorbar on the side
19 axis equal;
20 hold off;
21 % ***** trisurf plot function
22 hn=zeros(1,num_x);
23 for ii = 1:num_x
24     hn(1,ii) = x_nod(1,ii)^2+x_nod(2,ii)^2;
25 end
26 % calculating the average value in each triangle:
27 he=zeros(1,num_e);
28 for ii = 1:num_e
29     n1 = e_nod(ii,1);
30     n2 = e_nod(ii,2);
31     n3 = e_nod(ii,3);
32     he(1,ii) = (1/3) * ( hn(1,n1) + hn(1,n2) + hn(1,n3) );
33 end
34 figure(3)
35 var_field = he;
36 trisurf(e_nod, x_nod(1,:)', x_nod(2,:)', x_nod(3,:) ', var_field);
37 view(0,90); % forcing the Oxy view
38 colorbar; % colorbar on the side
39 axis equal;
40 figure(4)
41 var_field = he;
42 trisurf(e_nod, x_nod(1,:) ', x_nod(2,:) ', x_nod(3,:) ', ...
43         var_field, 'linestyle','none')
44 colorbar; % colorbar on the side
45 axis equal;

```

Listing 15: Script for 2D plotting using Octave's built in functions. **plot2dmesh.m**

The first one, from line 4 to line 6, is the already mentioned **plot** function. Declaring the nodes as black circles (ko) allow to obtain figure 2(a).

In order to present the **scatter** function (lines 12 to 20), first, assume the following function,

$$f(x,y) = x \cdot y \quad (8)$$

Thus, each node will now possess its value, forming a variable field $f(x,y)$ (lines 8 to 11). The **scatter** function allows to plot a nodal discretization in which the nodes are painted with a color representing its field magnitude. However, the default **colorbar** of **scatter** function only presents the values between 0 and 1. To force the **colorbar** to present the true

Figure 1. (a) simple plot function. (b) Ox axis with logarithmic scale. (c) Oy axis with logarithmic scale. (d) Both Ox and Oy axis with logarithmic scale.

values of variable field $f(x, y)$, it is necessary the script in lines 15 and 16. The outcome of **scatter** function is presented in figure 2(b).

Another useful Octave's function for 2D (and 3D) plots is **trisurf** function. This function plots triangular elements and the plotting color of each triangle is related with its variable field. First, as shown in lines 22 to 25, a variable nodal field is established,

$$h_n(x, y) = x^2 + y^2 \quad (9)$$

Then, the nodal values are interpolated to the centre of each triangle, as shown in lines 27 to 33. Afterwards, **trisurf** function can be applied to plot the triangles with edges (line 36) or without edges (line 42 and 43). If the Oxy is to forced (allowing a true 2D view), the view option **view(0,90)** should be declared (line 39). The results of these two options are shown in figures 2(c) and (d).

4.2. 3D graphics

As for the 2D plots, a 3D mesh is also constructed to demonstrate some of Octave's 3D plotting functions. As Listing 16 shows, a structured 3D nodal mesh and the corresponding tetrahedral mesh are constructed.

```

1 % Structured 3D nodal mesh script: mesh3d.m
2 clc;
3 close all;
4 clear all;

```


Figure 2. (a) simple plot function. (b) function scatter with colorbar. (c) function trisurf with colorbar and triangular edges. (d) function trisurf without triangular edges.

```

5 L = 20; % dimension along Ox
6 D = 10; % dimension along Oy
7 H = 10; % dimension along Oz
8 div_L = 8; % number of division along Ox
9 div_D = 4; % number of division along Oy
10 div_H = 4; % number of division along Oz
11 % ***** nodal mesh
12 ind = 0; % counter
13 x_nod = zeros(3,1); % initialization of vector: x_nod
14 for ii = 1:div_L+1
15     for jj = 1:div_D+1
16         for kk = 1:div_H+1
17             ind = ind + 1;
18             x_nod(1,ind) = (L/div_L)*(ii-1); % x coordinate
19             x_nod(2,ind) = (D/div_D)*(jj-1); % y coordinate
20             x_nod(3,ind) = (H/div_H)*(kk-1); % z coordinate
21         end
22     end
23 end
24 num_x = ind; % number of nodes discretizing the problem's domain
25 % ***** triangle mesh (triangular elements)
26 ind = 0;
27 e_nod = zeros(1,3); % initialization of vector: e_nod
28 for ii = 1:div_L
29     for jj = 1:div_D
30         for kk = 1:div_H
31             n1 = (kk+0) + (jj-1)*(div_H+1) + (ii-1)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
32             n2 = (kk+1) + (jj-1)*(div_H+1) + (ii-1)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);

```

```

33     n3 = (kk+1) + (jj-0)*(div_H+1) + (ii-1)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
34     n4 = (kk+0) + (jj-0)*(div_H+1) + (ii-1)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
35     n5 = (kk+0) + (jj-1)*(div_H+1) + (ii-0)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
36     n6 = (kk+1) + (jj-1)*(div_H+1) + (ii-0)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
37     n7 = (kk+1) + (jj-0)*(div_H+1) + (ii-0)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
38     n8 = (kk+0) + (jj-0)*(div_H+1) + (ii-0)*(div_H+1)*(div_D+1);
39     % tetrahedral 1
40     ind = ind + 1;
41     e_nod(ind,1:4) = [n1 n4 n8 n3];
42     % tetrahedral 2
43     ind = ind + 1;
44     e_nod(ind,1:4) = [n1 n2 n3 n8];
45     % tetrahedral 3
46     ind = ind + 1;
47     e_nod(ind,1:4) = [n3 n7 n8 n2];
48     % tetrahedral 4
49     ind = ind + 1;
50     e_nod(ind,1:4) = [n2 n6 n7 n5];
51     % tetrahedral 5
52     ind = ind + 1;
53     e_nod(ind,1:4) = [n1 n2 n5 n8];
54     % tetrahedral 6
55     ind = ind + 1;
56     e_nod(ind,1:4) = [n5 n7 n8 n2];
57     end
58     end
59 end
60 num_e = ind; % number of elements discretizing the problem's domain

```

Listing 16: Script for constructing 3D structured meshes. **mesh3d.m**

With this script, a nodal mesh and a tetrahedral mesh are organized as arrays: **x_nod** and **e_nod**, respectively. Both arrays can be correspondingly represented as $[x]$ and $[e]$, being organized as follows

$$[x] = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_N \\ y_1 & y_2 & \cdots & y_N \\ z_1 & z_2 & \cdots & z_N \end{bmatrix} ; [e] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 7 \\ 3 & 1 & 4 & 6 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ N & N-2 & N-1 & N-4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Thus, as in the previous section, array **x_nod** contains the coordinates of each node of the nodal mesh, possessing a size $[3 \times N]$, in which N is the total number of nodes of the nodal mesh. Array **e_nod** possesses in each line the index of the 4 nodes forming the corresponding tetrahedron. Its size is $[N_e \times 4]$, being N_e the total number of tetrahedrons of the tetrahedral mesh.

In Listing 17 interesting 3D plotting features of Octave for numerical methods discretization techniques are shown.

```

1 % Plotting a structured 3D nodal mesh script: plot3dmesh.m
2 mesh3d; % calling mesh3d script
3 % ***** plotting the nodal mesh
4 figure(1)
5 plot3(x_nod(1,:),x_nod(2,:),x_nod(3:),'k. ');
6 axis equal;
7 % ***** scatter3 plot function
8 f=zeros(1,num_x);
9 for ii = 1:num_x
10     f(1,ii) = x_nod(1,ii)*x_nod(2,ii) + x_nod(3,ii)^2;
11 end
12 figure(2)
13 var_field = f;
14 hold on;
15 colorbar;
16 caxis([min(var_field) max(var_field)]);
17 scatter3(x_nod(1,:)', x_nod(2,:)', x_nod(3,:)', 20, var_field, 'filled')
18 view(30, 30); % forcing a specific view
19 colorbar; % colorbar on the side

```

```

20 axis equal;
21 hold off;
22 % ***** tetramesh plot function
23 hn=zeros(1,num_x);
24 for ii = 1:num_x
25     hn(1,ii) = ( x_nod(1,ii)^2+x_nod(2,ii)^2) * x_nod(3,ii);
26 end
27 % calculating the average value in each tetrahedron:
28 he=zeros(1,num_e);
29 for ii = 1:num_e
30     n1 = e_nod(ii,1);
31     n2 = e_nod(ii,2);
32     n3 = e_nod(ii,3);
33     n4 = e_nod(ii,4);
34     he(1,ii) = (1/4) * ( hn(1,n1) + hn(1,n2) + hn(1,n3) + hn(1,n4) );
35 end
36 var_field = he;
37 max_var_field = max(var_field);
38 min_var_field = min(var_field);
39 for ii = 1:num_e
40     delta_var = max_var_field-min_var_field;
41     int_var_field(1,ii)=1+(round(63*(var_field(1,ii)-min_var_field)/delta_var));
42 end
43 figure(3)
44 tetramesh(e_nod, x_nod', int_var_field);
45 view (30, 30); % forcing a specific view
46 colorbar; % colorbar on the side
47 axis equal;
48 figure(4)
49 tetramesh(e_nod, x_nod', int_var_field, 'linestyle','none')
50 colorbar; % colorbar on the side
51 axis equal;

```

Listing 17: Script for 3D plotting using Octave's built in functions. **plot3dmesh.m**

The first one, from line 4 to line 6, is the 3D version of the already mentioned **plot** function: the **plot3** function. Declaring the nodes as black circles (k.) allow to obtain figure 3(a).

Next, the **scatter3** function (lines 12 to 20) is presented. However, first, consider the following field function,

$$f(x,y,z) = x \cdot y + z^2 \quad (11)$$

Now, to each node it will be associated a value, forming a variable field $f(x,y,z)$ (lines 8 to 11). The **scatter3** function allows to plot in 3D a nodal discretization in which the nodes are colored in accordance with their field magnitude. Due to the limitations of the default **colorbar** for **scatter3** function (already mentioned), it is necessary to force the **colorbar** to present the true values of variable field $f(x,y,z)$ (lines 15 and 16). Function **scatter3** produces the results presented in figure 3(b).

Regarding 3D tetrahedral meshes, Octave possesses another useful function: **tetramesh** function. This function plots tetrahedral elements and the plotting color of each tetrahedron is related with its variable field. Thus, As lines 23 to 26 indicate, a variable nodal field is established,

$$h_n(x,y,z) = (x^2 + y^2) \cdot z \quad (12)$$

Afterwards, the nodal values are interpolated to the centre of each tetrahedron (lines 27 to 35). With the average values calculated, the tetrahedrons can be plotted with **tetramesh** function. As lines 44 and 49 indicate, the tetrahedrons can be plotted with edges (line 36) or without edges, respectively. A specific 3D view can be force with the view option **view(?,?)** (line 45).

Figure 3. (a) simple plot3 function. (b) function scatter3 with colorbar. (c) function tetramesh with colorbar and triangular edges. (d) function tetramesh without triangular edges.

5. FINAL REMARKS

Octave is a playground for mathematicians and engineers. It allows to program new numerical theories and easily visualize its results/outcomes. The vectorization capability of Octave is its strongest advantage, allowing to swiftly execute both simple linear and complex non-linear algorithms. Octave also provides user friendly graphical functions, allowing to easily plot data and outputs. As the bibliography shows (in the end of this manuscript), it is possible to find several books addressing Octave's programming for engineers.

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